

A Novel Method for Evaluating the Biodegradability of Polymers by Tracking Changes in Tensile Properties During Degradation

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Introduction

What happens with our trash?

The majority of plastic waste is either landfilled or dumped into the environment. Due to environmental concerns, materials that biodegrade without leaving micro- and nano-plastics are being developed. For example, "green composites" consisting of biodegradable polymers combined with natural fibers or biomass. Typically, biodegradability is evaluated by monitoring the CO₂ evolution of the material as it biodegrades in a controlled environment. However, these methods have significant limitations:

1. They cannot be used to **evaluate biodegradability in natural environments**
 2. Many researchers test in natural environments without standards, thus **results of different studies are not easily comparable**
- Thus, there is a need for more versatile methods to evaluation degradation, that should be **applicable in any environment.**

This research investigates...

...how the **mechanical properties of biodegradable materials change during degradation** and explore whether this relationship can be used to **evaluate biodegradability in diverse environments**

Experiments

1. Fabrication of test material

A prototype green composite was made from tree bark (60%) and polybutylene succinate (PBS, 40%). It was made by hot-kneading bark and PBS and then extrude into pellets. Dumbbell shapes were made by compression moulding of the pellets.

2. Biodegradation in simulated compost

Samples were placed in compost and kept in an incubator at 58°C and 100% relative humidity. The biodegrading material turns into CO₂ which is used to calculate the degree of biodegradation:

$$\frac{m_{CO_2}^{test} - m_{CO_2}^{blank}}{ThCO_2} \cdot 100 = D_t$$

In addition, specimens were extracted every 2 weeks for tensile testing.

3. Biodegradation in outdoor soil

Specimens were buried in a garden, where CO₂ cannot be measured. Instead, samples were extracted periodically and the change in tensile properties was measured. The experiment lasted 30 weeks (6 months).

$$ThCO_2 = \frac{44}{12} \cdot m_{tot} \cdot C_{tot}$$

- D_t : Degree of biodegradation (%)
- $m_{CO_2}^{test}$: CO₂ from material in compost (g)
- $m_{CO_2}^{blank}$: CO₂ from compost (blank) (g)
- $ThCO_2$: CO₂ from material at 100% biodeg. (g)
- m_{tot} : Dry solid mass of material (g)
- C_{tot} : Organic carbon content of material (g/g)

Results and Discussion

Composting experiment

The test material reached a biodegradation of 12.8 % after 8 weeks (56 days) in compost, as shown in Figure A.

Figure B shows how the tensile modulus and the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) decreased as biodegradation progressed. Linear curves were fitted to these data points.

Outdoor soil experiment and biodegradation estimation

Similar to the composting experiment, biodegradation in soil caused the tensile modulus and UTS to gradually decrease over time (Figure C).

The degree of biodegradation was estimated by extrapolating the x values in the linear curves in Figure B using the data in Figure C. Thus, it was estimated that after 6 months of soil burial, the composite had degraded by 7 to 9%.

Final Comment

The research continues with various biodegradable materials and specimen dimensions to investigate how tensile properties change during degradation in different natural environments, such as soil and seawater. We aim to develop evaluation methods that reflect the functional lifetime of materials, as opposed to traditional methods that focus solely on material conversion into CO₂.